

Stark transition (${}^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^3P_{1/2}$) may also be attributed⁷ to the presence of strong donor sites in the ligands 'PT', 'PFT' and 'PTT'.

Parameter of bonding ($b^{1/2}$) which measures the amount of metal-4f and ligand orbital mixing, and covalency-angular overlap parameter (η) which is also related to nephelauxetic ratio (β), are calculated by using the relations^{7,8},

$$\beta = \frac{\bar{\nu}_{\text{complex}}^0}{\bar{\nu}_{\text{aquo}}}$$

$$b^{1/2} = \left[\frac{1}{2} (1 - \beta) \right]^{1/2}$$

$$\eta = \frac{(1 - \beta^{1/2})}{\beta^{1/2}}$$

$$\delta(\%) = [(1 - \beta)/\beta] \times 100$$

In all of the present Nd^{III} complexes the positive and very small values of $b^{1/2}$ indicate poor covalency of the complexes. It is also supported by the calculated values of $\beta({}^4G_{5/2})$ (0.986 6–0.995 9) and $\beta({}^3P_{1/2})$ (0.998 2–0.999 5). Here the values of $\delta(\%)$ are found much below 1.5, which also suggests^{8,9} weak covalent bonding as well as weak metal–ligand interactions.

Ir spectra: On complexation, the blue-shift observed in $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ of imine-nitrogen, symmetric and asymmetric ($\nu_{\text{C=C}} + \nu_{\text{C=N}}$) of pyridine ring as well as decrease in pyridine-ring-breathing modes clearly ascertain⁹ involvement of imine-N and pyridin-N in coordination, while a decrease in $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ alongwith decrease in band intensity is indicative of metal–sulphur bond¹⁰. The strong bands observed at 610 and 595 cm^{-1} in the free ligand 'PFT' assigned¹¹ to ring-deformation modes, show red-shift of 15–25 cm^{-1} on complexation, indicating metal–ligand bond through furfuryl-oxygen. Strong bands observed at 640 and 572 cm^{-1} and medium bands at 490 and 471 cm^{-1} in free ligand 'PTT' possibly assigned¹¹ to thiophene (C=C) out-of-plane bending modes and (C–S–C) in-plane bending modes, respectively, also show red-shift of 20±5 cm^{-1} indicating involvement of thiophenyl sulphur on coordination. In all the present complexes, the medium and weak intensity bands observed in far-ir region at 523–507, 469–429, 331–317 and 281–270 cm^{-1} , tentatively assigned¹² to $\nu_{\text{M-imine-N}}$ ('PFT' and 'PTT' complexes only), $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$, $\nu_{\text{M-Py-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-Cl}}$, respectively, also confirm the octahedral stereochemistry of the ligands 'PT', 'PFT' and 'PTT' around Nd^{III} ion as represented below.

Nd^{III} complex with 'PT'

Nd^{III} complexes¹² with
'PFT', where x=O
'PTT', where x=S
and $\alpha = \text{Cl}/\text{NO}_2/\text{ClO}_4$

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Lanthanide(III) Iodide Complexes of 5,6-Benzoquinoline and 2-Ethoxycarbonylaminopyridine

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It is apparent that the ability of lanthanide ions to coordinate with neutral N-donors could best be evaluated in non-aqueous media, and a number of cationic or neutral complexes containing N-donor ligands have been isolated utilising non-aqueous media. In view of this, we report herein the coordinating ability of lanthanide(III) iodides with 5,6-benzoquinoline (Benzqn) and 2-ethoxycarbonylaminopyridine (ECAP). Lanthanide(III) perchlorate complexes of Benzqn are already known¹.

Experimental

The ligand 5,6-benzoquinoline (E.Merck) was used as such. The ligand 2-ethoxycarbonylaminopyridine was prepared² from 2-aminopyridine.

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ mol^{-1}	Mol. wt. Found/ (Calcd.)	μ_{eff} B.M.
			Ln	N	I			
[La(Benzqn) ₆ I] ₂	Green	330d	8.63 (8.72)	5.16 (5.26)	23.61 (23.90)	49.36	535 (1 594)	Diamag.
[Pr(Benzqn) ₆ I] ₂	Dull green	350d	8.72 (8.83)	5.15 (5.26)	23.58 (23.87)	51.16	537 (1 596)	3.49
[Nd(Benzqn) ₆ I] ₂	Green	360d	8.90 (9.00)	5.14 (5.25)	23.56 (23.82)	47.36	540 (1 599)	3.69
[Sm(Benzqn) ₆ I] ₂	Dull green	320d	9.27 (9.34)	5.13 (5.23)	23.50 (23.73)	50.93	542 (1 605)	1.69
[Gd(Benzqn) ₆ I] ₂	Light green	310d	9.62 (9.73)	5.12 (5.21)	21.21 (23.63)	49.82	540 (1 612)	7.81
[Tb(Benzqn) ₆ I] ₂	Black	360d	9.70 (9.85)	5.11 (5.20)	23.19 (23.60)	50.39	545 (1 614)	9.87
[Dy(Benzqn) ₆ I] ₂	Gray	360d	9.89 (10.04)	5.11 (5.19)	23.16 (23.55)	51.06	546 (1 618)	10.49
[Ho(Benzqn) ₆ I] ₂	Light green	360d	10.03 (10.18)	5.10 (5.18)	23.12 (23.51)	48.76	549 (1 620)	10.19
[Yb(Benzqn) ₆ I] ₂	Dull green	210	10.51 (10.62)	5.08 (5.15)	23.00 (23.40)	47.67	550 (1 628)	4.63
[La(ECAP) ₆ I] ₂	Brown	110	11.62 (11.73)	9.39 (9.45)	31.81 (32.17)	50.06	396 (1 184)	Diamag.
[Pr(ECAP) ₆ I] ₂	Brown	90	11.73 (11.88)	9.38 (9.44)	31.61 (32.12)	51.29	398 (1 186)	3.58
[Nd(ECAP) ₆ I] ₂	Reddish brown	98	10.51 (10.62)	10.18 (10.33)	27.81 (28.11)	47.63	454 (1 355)	3.51
[Sm(ECAP) ₆ I] ₂	Brown	78	10.89 (11.02)	10.16 (10.28)	27.36 (27.99)	51.09	456 (1 361)	1.55
[Gd(ECAP) ₆ I] ₂	Dark brown	140	11.36 (11.47)	10.12 (10.23)	27.24 (27.85)	49.93	457 (1 368)	7.89
[Tb(ECAP) ₆ I] ₂	Dull yellow	90	11.49 (11.60)	10.11 (10.21)	27.16 (27.81)	50.69	460 (1 370)	9.69
[Dy(ECAP) ₆ I] ₂	Light brown	84	11.71 (11.83)	10.10 (10.19)	27.13 (27.73)	51.01	462 (1 374)	10.63
[Ho(ECAP) ₆ I] ₂	Brown	92	11.84 (11.99)	10.08 (10.17)	27.11 (27.68)	48.83	463 (1 376)	10.28
[Yb(ECAP) ₆ I] ₂	Yellowish brown	106	12.40 (12.50)	10.01 (10.11)	27.09 (27.52)	48.09	465 (1 384)	4.59

Preparation of metal complexes: All the complexes were prepared by the following general method. The hydrated lanthanide iodide (~0.5 g) was dissolved in acetone (10 ml), and the corresponding ligand (~1.0 g) was also dissolved in the same solvent (10 ml). The two solutions were mixed with constant stirring. Stirring was continued for 15 min, and then chloroform (10 ml) was added to it with constant stirring when the complex started separating out slowly. The complexes so obtained were separated by filtration under suction, washed well with chloroform and diethyl ether and dried at 110° in a vacuum-oven.

The metal content of the complexes was estimated as metal oxide. The physicochemical techniques used in the identification of complexes were performed as described earlier^{3,4}.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the complexes along with their colour and m.p. are given in Table 1. All the complexes are sensitive to atmospheric moisture and their colour changes on standing in open atmosphere. Conductance data in nitrobenzene show that the complexes behave as 1 : 2 electrolytes

in this solvent, indicating that only one of the iodide ions is coordinated to the metal ion while the two are non-coordinated. Thus, these complexes may be formulated as [Ln(Benzqn)₆.I]₂ and [Ln(ECAP)₆.I]₂. The molecular weight of the complexes in the same solvent further confirms the similar electrolytic behaviour.

The magnetic moment values of the complexes are given in Table 1. Comparison of these values with those observed for 8-hydrated sulphates⁵ and those calculated from uncomplexed ions⁶ indicates that the 4f-electrons cannot be of great significance in bond formation in these complexes. The compounds discussed herein show little deviation from the Van Vleck values although the simple Curie equation has been used.

The important infrared spectral bands of the complexes are presented in Tables 2 and 3.

Benzqn complexes: The spectra of 5,6-benzoquinoline and its metal complexes have been studied by several workers⁷. Eight bands attributed to C—C, C=N stretchings and ring vibrations occur in the range 1 610–1 380 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of free 5,6-benzoquinoline. Four absorptions in the same region (8a, 8b, 19a, 19b) have also been identified in the spectrum of pyridine part. The

NOTES

TABLE 2—PARTIAL IR FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹) OF LANTHANIDE(III) IODIDES COMPLEXES OF 5,6-BENZOQUINOLINE

Compd.	$\nu_{C=C}, \nu_{C=N}$ (stretch)		ν (ring vibration)	ν_{Ln-N}
Benzqn	1 610m, 1 535m, 1 570s, 1 500s	1 455s, 1 420m 1 390m	—	—
[La(Benzqn) ₃ I] ₃	1 635m, 1 618m, 1 575m, 1 510m	1 482m, 1 450m, 1 395m	390m	—
[Pr(Benzqn) ₃ I] ₃	1 642m, 1 622m, 1 572m, 1 505m	1 388m, 1 448m, 1 390m	392m	—
[Nd(Benzqn) ₃ I] ₃	1 640m, 1 620m, 1 572m, 1 508m	1 495m, 1 452m, 1 392m	392m	—
[Sm(Benzqn) ₃ I] ₃	1 645m, 1 625m, 1 575m, 1 512m	1 490m, 1 451m, 1 395m	395m	—
[Gd(Benzqn) ₃ I] ₃	1 638m, 1 622m, 1 571m, 1 505m	1 492m, 1 454m, 1 393m	385m	—
[Tb(Benzqn) ₃ I] ₃	1 640m, 1 615m, 1 575m, 1 508m	1 485m, 1 450m, 1 390m	398m	—
[Dy(Benzqn) ₃ I] ₃	1 635m, 1 620m, 1 673m, 1 510m	1 490m, 1 450m, 1 392m	380m	—
[Ho(Benzqn) ₃ I] ₃	1 642m, 1 620m, 1 675m, 1 510m	1 492m, 1 453m, 1 395m	395m	—
[Yb(Benzqn) ₃ I] ₃	1 640m, 1 622m, 1 672m, 1 510m	1 495m, 1 450m, 1 392m	399m	—

Thus, ECAP acts as a bidentate ligand, coordinating through hetero N-atom and O-atom of the amide group forming a stable six-membered ring^{1,2}. In far-ir region, ν_{Ln-O} and ν_{Ln-N} have been assigned at 430–410 and 390–370 cm⁻¹, respectively.

Electronic spectra: The absorption spectra of the lanthanide complexes have been measured in solids as well as in aqueous and non-aqueous solutions. Lanthanum(III) has no significant absorption in the visible region. The absorption bands of Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} in the visible and near ir region appear due to the transitions from the ground level ³H₄ and ⁴I_{9/2} to the excited J levels of the 4f-configuration, respectively. Some red-shift or nephelauxetic effect is observed in DMF solution of the complexes. This red-shift is usually accepted as evidence of a higher degree of covalency than existing in the aquo-complexes^{1,3,14}. In all the complexes, marked enhancement in the intensity of the bands have been observed. Thus, we can say rather little about the probable geometrical arrange-

TABLE 3—PARTIAL IR FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹) OF LANTHANIDE(III) IODIDES COMPLEXES OF 2-ETHOXYCARBONYLAMINOPYRIDINE

Compd.	Pyridine vibrations				Amide-I	Amide-VI	ν_{M-O}	ν_{M-N}
	$\nu_{C=C}, \nu_{C=N}, \nu$ (ring vibration)							
ECAP	1 580s, 1 545m, 1 470m, 1 000s, 770s				1 720s	550m	—	—
[La(ECAP) ₃ I] ₃	1 620s, 1 570w, 1 482m, 1 010m, 776s				1 700s	570m	415m	382m
[Pr(ECAP) ₃ I] ₃	1 605s, 1 568m, 1 480m, 1 008m, 775m				1 696s	586m	410w	380m
[Nd(ECAP) ₃ I] ₃	1 595m, 1 560m, 1 490m, 1 015m, 780m				1 702s	568m	418m	392m
[Sm(ECAP) ₃ I] ₃	1 592s, 1 570w, 1 490m, 1 018m, 792s				1 695s	570m	422m	385w
[Gd(ECAP) ₃ I] ₃	1 600s, 1 568w, 1 488m, 1 002 w, 785m				1 696s	590m	430m	375w
[Tb(ECAP) ₃ I] ₃	1 598m, 1 568w, 1 490m, 1 015m, 785s				1 698s	572m	428w	378m
[Dy(ECAP) ₃ I] ₃	1 600s, 1 556m, 1 846m, 1 010m, 778s				1 703s	570m	412w	380m
[Ho(ECAP) ₃ I] ₃	1 605s, 1 572w, 1 482m, 1 015m, 790m				1 700s	575m	415m	390w
[Yb(ECAP) ₃ I] ₃	1 608s, 1 568w, 1 486m, 1 008m, 790s				1 695s	582m	420m	368m

additional bands in the ligand may thus be associated with carbocyclic ring as suggested by Shindo and Tamura⁹. On complexation, these shifted to higher wave number, clearly indicating that the ligand is bonded with the metal through the hetero-nitrogen atom. Other important absorptions, i.e. C—H in-plane deformation, ring breathing and C—H out-of-plane deformations also show positive shifts on complexation further confirm the N-bonding. Upon complexation new bands appear in the region 395–380 cm⁻¹ which are tentatively assigned ν_{Ln-N} modes.

ECAP complexes: Assignments of the substituted-pyridine bands are based on Katritzky's data for uncomplexed ECAP⁹ and other work on mono-substituted pyridines^{10,11}. There is as usual in such complexes, a slight shift of most ring bands to higher wavenumber on coordination. Of the amide bands, the CO stretching (amide I) and out-of-plane bending (amide VI) modes can be used to diagnose O or N coordination. The decrease in frequency of band-I and the increase in frequency of band-VI on complex formation confirm that the amide group is O-bonded in all the complexes.

ment of the ligands in these complexes except that it will tend to minimise both electrostatic and steric inter-ligand interactions, while the coordination number will tend to be as high as allowed by the steric requirements of the ligands.

The DTA profiles of all the Benzqn complexes are identical in their major details. The weak endothermic peak at ca. 110° is due to the hygroscopic nature of the complexes. The strong endothermic peak at ca. 265° is due to the decomposition of the iodide and the exothermic peak at ca. 510° represents complete decomposition of the complex. The DTA curves of the ECAP complexes are all similar showing endothermic peak at ca. 115° which is due to the removal of absorbed water and another endo peak at ca. 285° due to decomposition of the iodide. Finally, an exothermic peak at ca. 690° represents complete decomposition.

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Experimental

$K_2[Zn(Etxant)_4]$ or $K_2[Cd(Etxant)_4]$ required for the synthesis of $MM'(Etxant)_4$ were prepared *in situ* in methanol-water mixtures as described previously¹⁻³. To the above Zn^{II} or Cd^{II} tetraxanthate solution $UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, $Pb(NO_3)_2$, $AgNO_3$, $VO_2SO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ or Tl_2SO_4 dissolved in the same solvent mixture was added in 1 : 1/1 : 2 molar ratios. The heterobimetallic xanthates thus precipitated were filtered, washed with methanol-water mixture and dried in vacuum.

The experimental details pertaining to analysis, magnetic susceptibility, molar conductance, electronic and infrared spectral measurements were the same as described in our previous papers^{1,2}. The relevant analytical data are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data show the formation of heterobimetallic compounds of the general formula $MM'(Etxant)_4$. The compounds do not melt but decompose in the temperature range 122–170°, and all are insoluble in water and common organic solvents except $VOZn(Etxant)_4$ and $VOCd(Etxant)_4$ which are slightly soluble in dimethyl sulphoxide. The insolubility of the complexes and their non-melting nature suggest their polymeric nature and this has precluded the determination of their molar conductance and molecular weights. The low values of molar conductance⁵ (2.34–4.6 $\Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$) for the oxovanadium(II) compounds indicate that they are non-ionic. The μ_{eff} values (1.69–1.74 B.M.) for $VOZn(Etxant)_4$ and $VOCd(Etxant)_4$ correspond to the usual one unpaired electron⁶. The dioxouranium and other bimetallic compounds are diamagnetic as expected.

The electronic spectral bands for a series of dithiocarbamate complexes of oxovanadium(II) have

Synthesis and Structural Studies on Heterobimetallic Tetrakisxanthates

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In previous papers^{1,2}, we reported the synthesis and characterisation of bimetallic xanthates of the type $MM'(Etxant)_4$, where, $M = Co^{II}$ or Ni^{II} ; $M' = Zn^{II}$ or Cd^{II} ; $Etxant = ethyl\ xanthate$, and their complexes with Lewis bases. Formation of heterobimetallic tetraxanthates in which one of the metal ion is Zn^{II} or Cd^{II} and the other is Ag^I , Tl^I , Pb^{II} , VO^{II} or UO_2^{II} are not known so far. Synthesis and structural studies of these complexes were therefore undertaken and the results of the investigation are reported in the present paper.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF $MM'(Etxant)_4$

Compd.	Colour	Decomp. temp. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
			M	M'	S
$VOZn(Etxant)_4$	Bluish green	>250	8.00 (8.27)	10.40 (10.60)	41.52 (41.76)
$VOCd(Etxant)_4$	Bluish green	170	7.55 (7.70)	16.56 (16.96)	38.52 (38.78)
$UO_2Zn(Etxant)_4$	Bright yellow	140	28.95 (29.06)	7.72 (7.96)	31.20 (31.37)
$UO_2Cd(Etxant)_4$	Bright yellow	>250	27.30 (27.50)	12.84 (12.97)	29.42 (29.66)
$PbZn(Etxant)_4$	Light yellow	122	27.20 (27.50)	8.48 (8.63)	33.70 (33.99)
$PbCd(Etxant)_4$	Light yellow	142	25.46 (25.87)	13.84 (14.00)	31.68 (32.00)
$Ag_2Zn(Etxant)_4$	Light yellow	153	28.05 (28.34)	8.18 (8.53)	33.65 (33.95)
$Ag_2Cd(Etxant)_4$	Light yellow	124	26.32 (26.69)	13.71 (13.84)	31.42 (31.64)
$Tl_2Zn(Etxant)_4$	Light yellow	>250	42.46 (42.83)	6.20 (6.18)	26.39 (26.83)
$Tl_2Cd(Etxant)_4$	Light yellow	144	40.28 (40.75)	10.92 (11.18)	25.27 (25.57)